

percentage of unfilled grains on the percentage of leaves damaged was studied. The regression equation for grain yield on percentage of leaves damaged was $\hat{Y} = 1.9234 - 0.0149 X$, with a highly significant ($P = 0.01$) r^2 value of 0.409 (Fig. 1). A 10% increase in damaged leaves reduced yield by 0.15 g/tiller.

The regression equation for percentage of unfilled grains on percentage of damaged leaves was $\hat{Y} = 13.3005 + 0.2276 X$, with a significant ($P = 0.05$) r^2 value of 0.193 (Fig. 2). A 10% increase in the damaged leaves increased the unfilled grains by 2%. □

2. Regression of percentage of unfilled grains on percentage of leaves damaged by leaf-folder. (n = 120)

Rice yield losses caused by leaffolder damage to the flag leaf

Sellamal Murugesan and S. Chelliah, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée is an important rice insect in Tamil Nadu. Infestation is common at maximum tiller or flag leaf stages.

Flag leaves of potted IR20 plants were artificially infested with one 4th-instar larva/tiller. Feeding was confined to the flag leaf. Uninfested plants were the check. Four days after infestation, the larva was removed and damage was recorded as percent of the total area of the leaf. Grains from individual infested tillers were collected at maturity and percent unfilled grains was calculated. Healthy grain weight was recorded and lost grain yield was calculated.

Flag leaf damage ranged from 5 to 85% in different tillers and was categorized as <25, 26-50, 51-75, and >75%. Leaf area damage up to 50% reduced mean yield per tiller by 47%. When insect damage exceeded 75%, yield was reduced 70% (see table).

1. Regression of grain yield on percentage of flag leaf area damaged by leaffolder. Top: 2. Regression of unfilled grains on percentage of flag leaf area damaged by leaffolder.

Effect of flag leaf damage by leaffolder on rice grain yield.^a

Leaf area damage (%)	Mean yield (g/tiller)	Yield reduction (%)
<25	1.1	47
26-50	1.1	
51-75	1.2	46
>75	0.7	70
Uninfested	2.2	

^aMean of 8 replications.

The regression of grain yield on percent of leaf area damaged and percent of unfilled grains on percent of leaf area damaged was studied.

The regression equation of grain yield on the percentage area damaged was $\hat{Y} = 1.7274 - 0.0132 X$, with a highly significant ($P = 0.01$) r^2 value of 0.418 (Fig. 1). A 10% increase in leaffolder damage reduced yield by 0.13 g/tiller.

The regression equation of percentage unfilled grains on percent flag leaf damage was $\hat{Y} = 9.8758 + 0.4522 X$, with a highly significant ($P = 0.01$) r^2 value of 0.624 (Fig. 2). A 10% increase in flag leaf damage increased unfilled grains by 4.5%/tiller. □

Efficacy of insecticides against rice whorl maggot

H. M. Singh and S. M. A. Rizvi, Entomology Department, N. D. University of Agriculture and Technology (NDUAT), Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

Chlorpyrifos 10 G (coroban), carbosulfen 3 G (furadan), and monocrotophos 40 EC (Monocil) were tested for control of rice whorl maggot (RWM) *Hydrellia philippina* at the NDUAT Crop Research Station during 1981 kharif. Saket 4 was

planted in 5 × 4m plots. Insecticides were applied to 10-day-old nursery seedlings 10 days after transplanting. Insecticide granules were broadcast and monocrotophos was sprayed. RWM infestation was recorded 30 days after transplanting

by counting total and damaged leaves on 10 randomly selected plants from each plot. Data were statistically analyzed after angular transformation (see table).

Results showed all treatments to be significantly superior to the control. However, chlorpyrifos 10 G was most effective when applied 10 days after transplanting. Monocrotophos 40 EC achieved similar results whether applied in the nursery or in the field after transplanting. □

Insecticide control of RWM.

Insecticide formulation	Dose (kg ai/ha)	% RWM incidence (av of 3 replications)
<i>10 days after nursery sowing</i>		
Chlorpyrifos 10 G	1.0	14
Carbofuran 3 G	0.5	16
Monocrotophos 40 EC	0.5	17
<i>10 days after transplanting</i>		
Chlorpyrifos 10 G	1.0	5
Carbofuran 3 G	0.5	10
Monocrotophos 40 EC	0.5	16
Control		22
CD at 5%		3.29

Effect of blends of custard-apple oil and neem oil on survival of *Nephotettix virescens* and tungro virus transmission

V. Mariappan and R. C. Saxena, IRRI

Although *N. virescens*, the vector of the rice tungro virus (RTV), is still effectively controlled with insecticides in the tropics, their extensive use may cause insecticide resistance, as has happened in Japan on a closely related species, *N. cincticeps*. Recent studies at IRRI demonstrated that custard-apple *Annona squamosa* and neem *Azadirachta indica* oils significantly reduced *N. virescens* survival and RTV transmission on rice seedlings. Custard-apple oil contains several alkaloids and glycerides of hydroxylated unsaturated acids, and neem reduces insect populations because of several bitters or limonoids. Combinations of the oils were tested to determine if blends would improve pest control activity.

Custard-apple oil and neem oil, emulsified in water individually and as 1:1, 1:2, 1:4 (vol/vol) blends in 1% liquid detergent, were tested at 5, 10, and 20% oil concentrations. Ten-day-old TN1 rice seedlings were sprayed 3 hours before they were exposed to viruliferous *N. virescens*. Control plants were sprayed with a 1% detergent solution. The seedlings were placed in 1.5 × 15 glass test tubes and covered with polyvinyl caps.

Viruliferous insects that had a 4-day acquisition feeding on RTV-infected TN1 plants were released singly into each test tube for inoculation feeding. After 24 hours, the seedlings were transplanted in pots. Individual, fresh, oil-sprayed seed-

Table 1. Survival of *Nephotettix virescens* 1, 2, and 3 days exposure to TN1 rice seedlings sprayed with custard-apple oil (CAO) and neem oil (NO).^a IRRI, 1983.

Treatment	Oil concn (%)	Insect survival ^b (%)		
		1 day	2 days	3 days
CAO	5	62 cd	25 cd	5 c
CAO	10	52 d	15 de	0 c
CAO	20	19 efg	2 fg	0 c
NO	5	82 b	50 b	19 b
NO	10	70 bc	34 bc	7 bc
NO	20	52 d	17 de	0 c
CAO + NO (1:1)	5	29 e	7 ef	0 c
CAO + NO (1:1)	10	16 efg	1 fs	0 c
CAO + NO (1:1)	20	7 g	0	0 c
CAO + NO (1:2)	5	23 efg	3 ffg	0 c
CAO + NO (1:2)	10	16 efg	4 fg	0 c
CAO + NO (1:2)	20	7 g	0	0 c
CAO + NO (1:4)	5	13 efg	0	0 c
CAO + NO (1:4)	10	10 fg	0	0 c
CAO + NO (1:4)	20	9 g	0	0 c
Control (water + 1% liquid detergent)	0	100 a	100 a	97 a

^aAverage of 5 replications, 320 insects/replication. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 2. Rice tungro virus (RTV) infection in TN1 rice seedlings sprayed with custard-apple oil (CAO) and neem oil (NO) after exposure to viruliferous insects.^a IRRI, 1983.^a

Treatment	Oil concn (%)	RTV infection (%) of TN1 seedlings ^b		
		1 day	2 days	3 days
CAO	5	38 d	16 de	2 d
CAO	10	34 de	12 de	0 d
CAO	20	23 fg	7 ef	0 d
NO	5	67 ab	40 b	15 b
NO	10	56 c	28 c	8 c
NO	20	58 bc	20 cd	0 d
CAO + NO (1:1)	5	25 efg	6 fg	0 d
CAO + NO (1:1)	10	21 fg	0 i	0 d
CAO + NO (1:1)	20	11 i	0 i	0 d
CAO + NO (1:2)	5	21 fg	7 ef	0 d
CAO + NO (1:2)	10	19 fg	3 gh	0 d
CAO + NO (1:2)	20	15 ghi	0 i	0 d
CAO + NO (1:4)	5	17 fgh	3 gh	0 d
CAO + NO (1:4)	10	14 ghi	3 ghi	0 d
CAO + NO (1:4)	20	11 hi	1 hi	0 d
Control (water + 1% liquid detergent)	0	69 a	56 a	36 a

^aAverage of 5 replications, 320 seedlings/replication at the start. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.